

Compositional Solution and Color in the Interior

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Annotation:

The Article gives information about compositional resolution in interior and can be used as the alphabet for students and designers. It would be great, if the author enlarges the Article and writes the book later.

Keywords: Convenience, Subject or purpose, Integrity and style, Beauty, Color harmony.

The most important thing when drawing interior projects is to find the right compositional solution. It is required to find a unique composite solution for residential building interiors, and a unique composite solution for public building interiors.

For example: Let's look at the example of residential building interiors. There are different rooms in our house where we live. Living room, office, bedroom, kitchen, children's room, etc. The hotel is the most important room for all of us. Waiting for guests is one of our age-old traditions inherited from our generations. That's why we pay a lot of attention to it. An elegant compositional solution should be found in the hotel. It is necessary to find mutual harmony in the compositions on the ceiling and walls. That is, the compositions in them should be connected to each other, aimed at one goal or able to illuminate one topic. In this case, the designer should imagine the interior as a whole. In addition, the materials used in the interior, their colors are important. There are aspects to consider when designing any interior. Their sequence is shown below.

1. Convenience.
2. Subject or purpose.
3. Integrity and style.
4. Beauty.
5. Color harmony.

6. Material quality.

Just as architecture is different in different countries, interior decoration is also different. It depends on the geographical location, nature and people of that country.

The compositional solution in the interior, the combination of colors, doors and windows, and even their sizes are determined depending on the purpose for which the buildings were built. For example, (hospital, restaurant, school, hotel, etc.).

The interior parts of the building are divided into 3 types.

- a) Main part. For the main function of the building
- b) Auxiliary parts.
- c) Communication parts.

There are different schemes of composition.

all under the cover, markets ----- Hall

Cinema and exhibition halls. ----- Centralized

Department store, supermarket, museums. ----- Enfilade

buildings connecting to each other through a communication corridor on one or both sides. -----

Sectional houses with a corridor Sectional composition is combined to form a whole mixed interior.

----- hall and enfilade.

One of the main aspects in the organization of residential and public building interiors is the effect of the compositional solution in the interior on the human psyche. It is quite difficult to find an artistic solution to this process in the interiors of buildings with the same construction. Decorative materials for interior decoration, decorative plasters, mineral, textured, textured paints, marble on the floor, ceramic tiles, especially magnificent and decorative applied art samples play an important role in this. The compositional solution in the interior must necessarily have a center.

Based on the theme, the composition in the center is found and placed.

**Figure 1. "Tajmakhhal" wedding hall in the city of Fergana. Designer: Kasimov O.S.
Architect: Asomov R.**

In finding this solution, we refer to the laws of composition that we learned in the Basics of Composition lesson. They are Rhythm, Meter, Dynamics, Statics, Contrast, Nuance, etc.

Dynamics--- indicates a certain movement of the composition.

Static --- indicates the absence of movement in the composition.

Contrast --- opposition, Nuance means proximity to each other, harmony. Contrast and nuance are evident in the brilliance of colors.

In addition to these, laws such as proportion, scale, and balance provide the main support in finding a compositional solution. These compositions should be focused on one goal. It is also very important to keep the rhythm in this direction. We can compare it to the rhythm in music. These composite solutions can be implemented on ceilings and walls, with flat or embossed methods. Location of windows and doors. They should be placed in the west, east, north, and south directions. In addition, the placement of furniture and lighting also play an important role. In addition to the color and shape of the materials used for the interior design, the designer should know their beneficial or harmful aspects, as well as their constructive aspects. Because people trust the designer and entrust their homes.

Compositions in the interior use horizontal and vertical linear compositions. The designer should know how to use them properly. Because it has a great impact on the human psyche. If the ceiling of the room is low, it will be appropriate to come up with a compositional solution with a vertical line. Vertical lines make the room look taller.

Color and interior

The role of colors in the interior is incomparable. If they are not used correctly, a beautifully thought out compositional solution will look boring. There are 7 natural colors in life, which are reflected in the rainbow.

1. red
2. goldsmith
3. yellow
4. green
5. the apostle
6. Blue

7. violet

If we look closely, there are 3 different colors in nature. They are

1. red
2. yellow
3. Blue

Figure 2. Change from color to color. Babajanova Umida - 2nd grade student

The rest of the colors come from a mixture of these 3 different colors. There are also black and white, which are not included in the color range. Take white and black paints and mix them with the main colors red, yellow, blue. As a result, you will find several thousand different colors.

Warm and cool colors

Colors are divided into warm and cold colors. Warm colors are red, golden, yellow. Cold colors are green, blue, purple. different people like different colors. This is related to the human psyche. That's why we have to be very careful when using colors. Another important aspect is that most of the human life is spent indoors. Some colors make people active, while others calm them down. Some colors bring down a person's mood, some of them are uplifting and happy.

We use bright colors to decorate children's playgrounds and rooms.

Figure 3. Children's playground in Kibrai Designer: Kasimov.O.S

And in public buildings we use more calming colors.

Color is the most convenient tool for shaping the environment in which people live and creating conditions in it. All the furniture produced for the interior may be similar in terms of shape, but the possibilities in color are very wide. Color is up to the individual. Colors have a significant impact on the character of the room, revealing possibilities such as coziness, aesthetic appearance, individuality. The owner of any profession can express himself with colors. Color has a certain psychological and physiological effect on people in any case.

Green color is recommended for the training zone, it makes a person prone to rhythmic work or relaxation at the same time. Air color helps to create comfort in the rooms.

If the walls are painted with red color, it can quickly make a person tired and nervous, but this color has a positive effect on the psychology of children.

Yellow is recommended for children's rooms or playgrounds, just like red.

Yellow color combined with sunlight can sometimes make a person tired. But recently, the use of these bright colors has become a tradition in the exterior. We have to focus on one thing, we can mix any color with white or black, and we can find several thousand different colors.

White surfaces reflect more light, so they reflect the relief of objects better than other colors.

If the room seems narrow to you, we recommend using blue or gray colors for the walls. Then their level will appear expanded. If the room is too long, if you want to shorten it a little, then it is recommended to paint the walls in golden red, terracotta color. In this case, composite solutions on the ceiling and wall play an important role. We cannot imagine color in the interior in isolation from other things. The colors of the walls, ceiling and furniture affect each other. Their colors should be harmonious with each other. Tonal relationships affect the perception of space.

If we decorate the interior with contrasting colors, the interior of the room will appear smaller, and on the contrary, if we decorate it with nuanced colors, the room will appear larger. There is another important aspect in painting the interior, the location of the windows facing south or north. If the windows face south, it is appropriate to use cold colors in the room. If the windows face north, the colors should be chosen warm, because natural light from the north side is very little. These recommendations are not mandatory. You can design the house you live in as you wish. They say that there is no argument about taste.

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